

IMPACT OF INDO-PHILIPPINES RELATIONS ON REGIONAL DYNAMICS

Talha Afzal^{*1}, Dr. Muhammad Hatim²

^{*1}MPhil Scholar, Department of Politics and International Relations, University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan

²Assistant Professor, Department of Politics and International Relations, University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan

Corresponding Author: *

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
27 November, 2024	27 December, 2024	11 January, 2025	18 January, 2025

ABSTRACT

The burgeoning cooperation between India and the Philippines has far-reaching implications for regional dynamics, extending beyond traditional diplomatic relations. The visit of Indian Foreign Minister Subrahmanyam Jaishankar to the Philippines underscores the strengthening ties between the two nations. This paper provides an in-depth analysis of India's Act East policy, its deepening engagement in East Asia, and the burgeoning cooperation opportunities between India and the Philippines. The cooperation between India and the Philippines has significant implications for the region, particularly in the context of the South China Sea dispute. The Philippines' territorial claims in the West Philippine Sea are supported by India, which has emphasized the importance of adhering to international law and respecting the sovereignty and sovereign rights of nations. This stance is crucial in promoting stability and security in the Indo-Pacific region. This paper explores the impact of Indo-Philippines cooperation on neighboring countries, the escalating tensions between China and ASEAN nations, and the decisive role of the South China Sea in regional dynamics. By examining these factors, this research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the implications of Indo-Philippines relations on regional stability and security.

Keywords: Act East Policy, ASEAN, Indo-Pacific, Regional Dynamics, South China Sea

INTRODUCTION

Indian Foreign Minister Subrahmanyam Jaishankar came to the Philippines from March 25 to 27 2024 to reaffirm support on the Philippine sovereignty and ASEAN treaties and to enhance bilateral cooperation in defense and security. Both Foreign Secretary Enrique Manalo of the Philippines and Jaishankar of India during a joint press briefing in Manila reiterated to uphold peace in Indo-Pacific region (Limaye 2024).

This exercise is a part of India foreign policy outreach to East Asia, which is a strategic foreign policy direction of the country. With this change in geopolitical realities of South Asia and with China stepping into this region as developing power Indo-Pacific has become centre of attention. India's economic progress as well as

reorientation toward the West, notably the US, enable it to act as a counterweight against China (Panda 2024).

The countries in the Indo-Pacific region pose strategic vulnerabilities regarding issues of interest. Today, ASEAN and its funding partners, Japan and India, seek to maintain a US propped liberal international system and open Sea Lines of Communication often challenged by an ascending China. Specifically, India has apprehensions to its maritime liberties and strategic alliance with regional states in Southeast Asia because of China (Panda 2024b; Pant and Milford 2021).

ASEAN-India Economic Engagement

The grouping of countries includes Brunei, Thailand Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar, Malaysia, Indonesia, Philippines, Singapore, Vietnam and Timor Leste collectively contribute to 11.3 % of Indian foreign trade. ASEAN-India trade value was USD 131.5 Billion during the FY 2022-2023. The negotiation of the ASEAN-India Trade in Goods Agreement (AITIGA) in 2009 led to the liberalisation of non-tariff measures and trade improvements in transparency (De 2023).

Since the Eisenhower administration in the Philippines, each successive administration has managed relations with China delicately. Whilst, President Benigno Aquino III aimed at managing the ASEAN power with China's naval assertiveness through the arbitration; President Rodrigo Duterte has tilted towards the Chinese inclination through the ASEAN-China option of conduct (De Castro 2020). But the new President Ferdinand Marcos Jr administration yet again reformed its foreign policy aligning it with the US and focusing on the arbitral award of 2016 on South China Sea and sovereignty (De Castro 2023).

However, ASEAN's shifting foreign policy strategies have varied greatly between the effort to balance China's power and maintaining an affinity with external powers, particularly the United States. Aquino III's arbitration pushed for legal sovereignty, while Duterte's tilt toward China implied a pragmatic one. Marcos Jr.'s pivot to the US represents a return to a rules based order, but it could atomize ASEAN unity and make regional pursuits of stability even more challenging in an increasingly geopolitical tension charged era.

India's Act East Policy

The main changes in India 's post Cold war foreign policy came into perspective in the year 1991. Liberalization and dismantlement of license permit raj let India seize opportunities to get operational in the international market, to embrace multi dimension diplomacy, to start the 'Look East' policy by Narsimha Rao government in 1992. Starting from economic cooperation, the policy over time reached strategic cooperation and at the moment under PM Narendra Modi involved in Act East policy since 2014 (Soulodre and Kesavan 2020; Lee and Lee 2020).

India had scaled an exchange of USD 131.5 billion with ASEAN during the financial year 2022-2023. Today more than 50% of the tradewith partners outside India passes through

the South China Sea which signifies that India needs good relations with the moderate partners of South East Asia and the Far East. India's interactions over and above its trade relations are defense relations, maritime security, and capacity building (Khanna and Kaur).

India's shift of its foreign policy towards post Cold War has been driven by a strategic shift from globalization and regional integration. Narsimha Rao's 'Look East', and its evolution into 'Act East' under Narendra Modi, demonstrates that India's eastward looking economic and strategic partnerships are priority areas. Although economic cooperation with ASEAN is important, economic reliance on the South China Sea as a transportation route makes striking the right balance between assertive defense and security collaborations on one side, and building trade relations with ASEAN on the other side, critical to the Philippines. The trouble, however, is that the development of a more neutral policy in an increasingly sensitive geopolitical location will require India to have a working relationship with the powers in the region, without sacrificing its strategic autonomy.

Indo-Philippines Bilateral Relations Economic Cooperation

India and the Philippines are experiencing constant growth in the bilateral trade out of which Philippines has great export potential in IT, Pharmaceutical and Health Care, Tourism, Agriculture & Food Products & Renewable Energy Industries. The MEA to be specifically discussed in this paper is the India-Philippines Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA), the objectives of which are to decrease trade barriers, and therefore increase the level of bilateral trade. The approximate investment made by Indians in the Philippines is over a billion USD, and main companies investing are Tata Consulting Services, Tech Mahindra, etc., Sun Pharma, Lupin to name few. Consequently, many Philippine based firms such as AG&P and the AC Energy Corporation are now investing more in India.

Political Cooperation

India and Philippines opt for stronger diplomatic, strategic ties; improve relations under Ferdinand Marcos Jr. During this year's 20th ASEAN-India Summit meeting, in Jakarta in October 2023, President Marcos Jr., together with Prime Minister Narendra Modi, outlined this positive trajectory. The deepening political and bilateral

engagement is also demonstrated with the visit of Secretary Gideon Manalo in India who also led the 5th Joint Commission on Bilateral Cooperation. India's position on supporting a 'Free and Open Indo Pacific' strikes a chord with the Philippines' positioning with the U.S. and inside the QUAD framework. It is an evolving partnership, one in which we work together in an aligned way to address our common challenges and realise opportunities in the broader Indo Pacific region.

Bilateral Cooperation: Defense and Maritime Security

The military relationship between India and Philippines has intensified with the sale of BrahMos missiles to Philippines and such approaches exemplifies India's bigger diplomatic framework where India is trying to bolster the capabilities of Southeast Asian states to counter the pressures they face from the regional power like China without resorting to using force.

Moreover, similar to the military exercises, which the two countries held, there is greater emphasis on joint naval exercises as well as maritime security efforts; this highlights a mutual understanding to maintain a cooperative international approach to the Indo Pacific region. These measures indicate India's readiness to participate in protecting important sea routes, fighting against pirates and helping in increasing awareness of the maritime environment.

Indo-Philippines relations have a strong defense cooperation as a fundamental element of the relations between the two states. Exercise Maitree held every year deals with counter insurgency and counter terrorism. Naval cooperation also involves military exercises, including SIMBEX besides defense transactions such as the sale of the USD 375 million BRAHMOS cruise missile, which marks a important export for India in defense (Gill 2023).

Table 1. Indian Navy's Presence in IOR, SCS & Indo-Pacific

2015	INS Kamorta was deployed to participate in the Langkawi International Maritime and Aerospace exhibition (LIMA-15) scheduled from 17 – 21 Mar 2015.
	INS Kamorta, Satpura took part in SIMBEX-15 in May 2015.
	INS Saryu, participated in a weeklong ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) Disaster Relief Exercise (DiREx) 2015 conducted in Penang, Northern Malaysia from 24 to 28 May 2015.
2016	INS Airavat participated in the ADMM Plus (ASEAN Defence Ministers' Meeting Plus) Exercise on Maritime Security and Counter Terrorism (Ex MS & CT) from 01 to 09 May 2016, which commenced at Brunei and culminated at Singapore, with various drills and exercises in the South China Sea.
	The Indian Navy's Eastern Fleet sailed out on 18 May 2016 on a two-and-a-half-month-long operational deployment to the South China Sea and North West Pacific. During this overseas deployment, the ships of Eastern Fleet made port calls at Cam Rahn Bay (Vietnam), Subic Bay (Philippines), Sasebo (Japan), Busan (South Korea), Vladivostok (Russia), and Port Klang (Malaysia).
	INS Sumedha arrived in Padang, Indonesia on 10 Apr 2016 to participate in the International Fleet Review and the second edition of the Multilateral Naval Exercise KOMODO (MNEK).
2019	INS Kamorta exercised with the Indonesian Warship KRI Usman Harun in the Bay of Bengal as part of the Indian Navy – Indonesian Navy Bilateral Exercise 'Samudra Shakti' from 6 to 7 November 2019.
2020	The 30th edition of the India-Thailand Coordinated Patrol (Indo-Thai CORPAT) between the Indian Navy and the Royal Thai Navy was conducted

	from 18 – 20 November 2020. Philippines participated as observer.
	The 35 th edition of the India-Indonesia Coordinated Patrol (IND-INDO CORPAT) between the Indian Navy and the Indonesian Navy was conducted from 17 to 18 December 2020.
	The 2020 edition of SIMBEX in the Andaman Sea. Philippines participated as observer.
	2nd edition of India, Singapore and Thailand Trilateral Maritime Exercise SITMEX-20, from 21 to 22 November in the Andaman Sea.
	The IN undertook PASSEX with the Royal Australian Navy (RAN) in the East Indian Ocean Region from 23 to 24 September 2020.
2021	India and the US on March 28 kicked off a two-day naval exercise in the eastern Indian Ocean region
Source: Premesha Saha, 2021. India Calibrates its South China Sea Approach (Observer Research Foundation)	

India's Balancing Act and Regional Perceptions

Gaging the India-Philippines relationships purely on military or diplomatic reasons is wrong, because both India and Philippines are addressing the needs of the evolving geopolitics of Indo-Pacific. On the other hand, a combination of growing China aggressiveness particularly with South China Sea and island building strategies has forced the regional states to look for diplomatic, economic and security partners, enabling India engagement in the region to serve such states objectives in reconstructing their great power relations. In its effort to grapple with Indo-US alliance politics, China has self-constructed India as a target: all its military and political activity including multiple defense agreements, joint naval exercises and economic agreements attempt to wrestle India out choking on its dominance.

Despite its alignment with the United States on several issues, India has historically pursued an independent foreign policy, and its deeper engagement in Southeast Asia raises questions about the sustainability of this approach in the face of intensifying great power competition. Additionally, India's strategic actions, while aimed at countering China's influence, require careful calibration to avoid alienating ASEAN nations that seek to balance their relationships with both India and China. The Philippines, like many other Southeast Asian states, navigates a complex foreign policy landscape where maintaining ties with China is often a necessity due to economic and geographic considerations. India's ability to foster trust and confidence

among its regional partners will be crucial in ensuring the long-term success of its engagement strategy (Lalremsiami & Patnaik, 2020).

The South China Sea Conundrum

Most of the South China Sea or SCS enjoys an importance due to the fact it contains a large reserve of oil and natural gas as well as acting as an important sea path that links the Pacific as well as the Indian Ocean. Sovereign assertive conflicts between China on one side and Vietnam, Malaysia, Brunei, and the Philippines added tension in the region. China has enticingly taken control of the militarization of the Spratly Islands and enhancing the issues of the freedom of navigation and sovereignty (Manhas 2022).

Looking at India's involvement in the SCS, it fits perfectly with the Indian ocean/Indo-Pacific strategy. The SCS is an important economic channel in the region and is significant for India. India has supported the UNCLOS principles and the 2016 arbitral award because it has supported the use of peaceful measure to solve dispute (Chong 2018). Yet, China's aggressive posturing has led the ASEAN states to look for more effective security alliances with India, for instance, the US and other actors (Panda 2024a).

The South China Sea is of critical strategic and economic importance because of its massive oil and natural gas reserves as well as its function as a main maritime transport route connecting the Pacific and Indian Oceans. With the militarization of the Spratly Islands and sovereignty claims, China has fomented regional tensions that constrain freedom of navigation,

and threaten smaller ASEAN states such as Vietnam, Malaysia, Brunei and the Philippines. India's involvement suits its Indo Pacific strategy adopting principles of UNCLOS and peaceful resolution of disputes including support for arbitral award of 2016. But ASEAN nations have now turned to stronger security partnerships with India, the U.S. and other allies out of fears over China's aggressive posturing.

Regional Implications of Indo-Philippines Relations

Acting East is a strategic policy of India and it particularly relies on the relations with ASEAN partners especially Philippines, Vietnam and Malaysia. The bilateral relationship between India and the Philippines is perfect model of cooperation in defense, trade and maritime security. All such cooperation assists in informing and reassuring the smaller southeast Asian nations taking a stand against China's rising aggression. India's participation in naval exercises and combination of efforts in the Indian ocean and its proactive attempts in economic integration to become part of the Asia-Pacific region clearly show its intentions to respect rules based system. BrahMos missile deal and other partnership with the Philippines demonstrate India's strategy to contain China's rise (Lalremisiami and Patnaik 2020). However, China sees India's increasing regional profile as a American-backed effort to challenge Beijing's dominion (Hong and Lu 2016).

India's 'Act East' policy has strategic emphasis in developing ties for the Philippines, Vietnam and Malaysia to forge a stable and strong regional relationship. Further, cooperation in defense, trade and maritime security with the Philippines, exemplifies cooperation in the bilateral relationship with the Philippines; providing for smaller Southeast Asian nations a model of countering China's assertiveness. As in its naval exercises, economic integration efforts and the BrahMos missile deal, India's approach to the Indo-Pacific has been rules based. Yet, China's interpretation of India's growing influence as part of an American concerted attempt to grapple its dominant position in the region presents risks of rising regional tensions which reduce India's own strategic autonomy and its delicate balancing act.

Conclusion

India has deepened diplomatic and economic relations with the Philippines are in line with the wider multi-dimensional approach to mend the

asymmetric bilateral relationship and regain the foothold in the Indo-Pacific aimed against China in order to protect Indian interests. The relations affecting both nations especially in military and naval domain have implications to regional dynamics. With conflicts continuing in the South China Sea, India continues to support international law and diplomacy, looking forward to peaceful resolution of such conflicts and enhancing security in the region through effective multilateralism. Thus, strengthening the relations with the ASEAN countries India also determines the further development of the Indo-Pacific region.

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